

Analysis Of Population Growth As Sociological Factor Affecting Sugarcane Productivity In Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Agriculture, Population growth, Sugarcane, Productivity, Sugarcane productivity</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5515637</p>	<p><i>Unchecked population growth especially in developing countries like Asia and Africa is posing many threats to the world's resources that limited. Like other sectors of society, population growth also affects agriculture sector as well. That's why the present study was designed to know about the influence caused by population explosion over agricultural production especially sugarcane. The study was conducted in two districts of Pakistan; Mardan and Charsadda where data was collected through interview schedule/questionnaire from 384 sugarcane growers who were selected through multistage random sampling technique from 12 Union Councils. Bivariate results of the study show that a positive attitude towards sale of agricultural land for residential purposes caused obvious reduction in sugarcane productivity as evident from a highly significant ($p=0.000$) and negative association ($T^c= -0.109$). Likewise, low investment in agricultural constrained sugarcane productivity as obvious form a highly significant ($p=0.000$) and negative ($T^c= -0.144$) association. Multivariate results show that farmers from middle socio-economic status group are worst affected in terms of sugarcane production than high socio-economic status groups due to land disputes. Involving religious and political leadership for awareness to control population and through the diffusion of new technologies production processes of sugarcane can be increased.</i></p>

Introduction

World population touched 7 billion during mid-year 2011 (Bloom, 2011) and it is projected that it would rise to about 8 billion in 2025, and by 2050 it will reach 9 billion people (Calend, 2013). Growing population is not only competing with agriculture sector for land and water resources but also exerting tremendous pressure on this sector to produce more. Therefore, the population growth may lead to food insecurity and food conflicts, malnutrition, and undernutrition among people. (Maxwell, 1995). Moreover, it might generate environmental problems and urban congestion (Magsi and Torre, 2013), where dense settlements put pressure on the land and other natural areas to meet their basic needs for subsistence. On the other side, intensive agricultural production to meet the growing population needs often leads to soil erosion, degradation, and increased salinity, which results in lower agriculture productivity. While this decline can occur in just a few years, but it will take decades to restore land productivity (Avenir Health (RAPID Model), 2017).

It is estimated that 99.9% of the world food is derived from land and the remaining less than 0.01% from the oceans (Pimentel & Pimentel, 1996). In fact, there are vast majority of the underfed people increase demand for food, which compel farmers around the world to cultivate their arable lands and not allow them to fallow the lands naturally to regenerate itself before cultivation is carried out again on the same land (FAO, 2002). Thus, it is quite logical that when the land is under serious threat due the immense increase in population, farmers will cultivate the same land intensively for multi-cropping production to meet the needs of the growing population. When farmers go for intensive cropping, there will be shift occurs from traditional to mechanized farming as they will use modern technology for cultivation. Traditional cropping methods in Asia, Africa and other countries in past were involved the rotation of crops which allow the land to fallow for time to allow it to regenerate its nutrients. But the increasing demand for food due to fast growing population, farmers put pressure on agricultural land without allowing any time off which negatively affect crop productivity negatively. Resultantly, the deterioration of soil starts which make the land completely dependent on synthetic fertilizers and uncontrolled irrigation. Therefore, farmers moving towards mechanized farming no longer depend on seasonal rain and at the same time, are totally dislodged from indigenous farming mechanisms. Due to mechanized farming, crop production increases, yet a complimentary notion develops when people usually care less about reducing the population (Karim, 2013).

The Malthusian and Neo-Malthusian perspective of the imbalances between population growth and resource growth seems functional in developing countries where population growth is surpassing the resource growth. The imbalance of population growth and low agricultural production is one such example of imbalances

in developing countries including Pakistan. Population growth has multi-dimensional influences in reducing agricultural production ranging from conversion of agricultural land into built environment, dumping of wastes in fertile lands and exhaustive use of agricultural land resources.

Literature review

Problems of growing population and agricultural land constraints are prominent now a days, as most of the people in rural areas are reside in densely populated areas due to which less land left for agricultural activities (Jayne et al., 2012).

The overwhelming increase in population and the conversion of urban and peri-urban land into non-agricultural, residential or industrial one in Pakistan (Francis et al., 2013; Samiullah, 2018), posed a serious threat to agricultural system that effect food security and decreased the productivity of important crops like sugarcane (Rahman et al., 2012).

Due to population growth and decrease in agricultural land, fallow periods of lands usually have been reduced. Consequently, most of the researchers found that with reduction in fallowing periods, soil fertility is degraded as well as crops productivity decline (Styger & Fernandes, 2006; Iheke and Ukandu, 2015).

Crops like sugarcane requires huge investment from government side as well besides the farmers in research and extension activities and giving loans and subsidies to the farmers (Goyal & Nash, 2017; Dubb, 2013), but due to enormous increase in population, the government is needed to focus and invest in other sector like education, health, etc. and removed such subsidies (Malaza and Myeni, 2009), due to which sugarcane productivity has negatively affected (Pervaiz et al., 2013; Mandla et al, 2011).

To feed the fast-growing population successfully, the agricultural productivity of crops must be speed up, which will lead to over cropping that ultimately led to the sapping and drain of the soil's nutrients, hence, drastically reducing yields or making crop cultivation not feasible. As the shrinking of cultivated land happening, there is enormous pressure on the available and to meet the need of the population. That is why hopes of the farmers are stacked with the new technology to show miracles to tackle this challenge otherwise the problems of poverty and hunger will remain persist till 2050 (Obaisi, 2017).

Research methodology

Study design

The current study was quantitative in nature, following cross-sectional design. This design was adopted because of its feasibility in social sciences where data is collected in one-shot from a cross section of population (Babie, 1989).

Universe, sampling procedure and sample size of the study

Two Districts (Charsadda and Mardan) of Central Valley of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan are top sugarcane producing areas of the province, therefore, these areas were selected for the current study. For the selection of the respondents, a multistage random sampling procedure was adopted by taking a series of steps. District Charsadda and Mardan were selected as universe of the study at first stage. District Mardan comprises of five tehsils (Tehsil Mardan, Takhtbhai, Katlang, Ghari Kapura & Rustam) and District Charsadda comprises of three tehsils (Tehsil Charsadda, Shabqadar and Tangi). Three Tehsils from each district were randomly selected at second stage. Furthermore, two union councils were selected from each tehsil (12 UCs in total) from which the number of farmers were assigned through proportional allocation method. Total population of the study universe (12 selected UCs), as counted through a pilot survey conducted by the researcher, comes out to be 3720 sugarcane growers. Keeping in view the number of variables and study population, the formula proposed by Chaudhry (2009) is used for sample size calculation as below.

$$n = \frac{N\hat{p}\hat{q}z^2}{\hat{p}\hat{q}z^2 + Ne^2 - e^2} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation-1}$$

N= total number of farmers in selected UCs = 3720, p = population proportion = 0.5, q = opposite proportion = (1-p) = 0.5, z = confidence level = 1.96, e = margin of error = 0.05, n= 384

The required sample size worked out based on above formula is 384 farmers. The calculated sample size was proportional allocated to each Union Council by using formula proposed by (Bowly, 1926).

Nature of the respondents

Respondents of the following characteristics were included in the study.

1. Farmers growing sugarcane in selected UCs
2. Age from 18 years and above

Tools of data collection

As the study was quantitative in nature, so, a well thought out Interview Schedule encompassing all the study variables, as given in the conceptual framework (see table 1), was devised for collecting quantitative data from randomly selected respondents. The items used for study measurement were pre-tested to 25 respondents (Kothari, 2004). The main purpose of the pre-test was to assure the understanding of the instrument items by the respondents and researcher, consistency and relevance of questions and to determine the time required to administer the instrument. The data was collected through a trained team of researchers under the supervision of the core investigator (researcher himself).

Conceptual framework of the study

Conceptual framework of the study consisted of one independent variable (population growth), one dependent variable (sugarcane productivity) and one background variable (socio-economic) variable. Socio-economic status of the farmers was composite of educational status of the farmers, monthly income and size of landholding. See table 1.

Table. 1 Conceptual framework of the study

Background variable	Independent variable	Dependent variable
Socio-economic status	Population growth	Sugarcane productivity

Ethical considerations and duration of the study

APA standard ethics for social data collection were adopted. The ethics were also approved from the departmental ethics committee. Prior consent of the respondents was solicited for data collection. The data was collected from the respondents who were willing to provide information. Before data collection, the respondents were briefed about the purpose of the study. The information was collected in isolation from other respondents. The data collection process took approximately six months.

Indexation and reliability analysis

In social sciences, indexation is used for assessment of the respondent's attitude about the study variables. For indexation purposes, the statements (items) in a variable must be two or more than two. Thus, index construction is combining two or more items in a variable (Nachmias&Nachmias, 1992).

At a multivariate level, independent variable (population growth) was indexed and cross-tabulated with dependent variable (sugarcane productivity) to find out variation in dependent variable is caused by the independent variable or are affected by control variable (socioeconomic status of the family) too. Before indexation, Cronbach's alpha was executed for measuring the reliability of the study scale. The test results show that the value of both variables, e.g., population growth (independent) and sugarcane productivity (dependent), was above 0.6. See Table.2, and hence, fulfilled the criteria of indexation.

Table 2 Reliability results of the variables

Variables	Cronbach's alpha
Population growth	.65
Sugarcane productivity	.87

Data analysis

For testing the association between independent and dependent variables, bi-variate analyses were carried out. Sugarcane productivity, as dependent variable, was categorized into three levels (above average, average and below average) and cross-tabulated with independent variables. Chi-square test given by Tai (1978) was used to determine the association among variables.

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(O_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}}$$

..... Equation-2

Multivariate analysis was undertaken for variation in sugarcane productivity due to population growth by controlling socio-economic statuses of the farmers as suggested by Ullah et al. (2020). **Results and discussions**

The results in table 3 show that for all those respondents who perceived that people were selling their agricultural lands for residential purposes, 19.6% earned above average net income from sugarcane production compared to 41.9% of those who believed people were not selling their agricultural lands for residential purposes and 34.8% of those who were uncertain in this respect. A positive attitude towards sale of agricultural land for residential purposes caused obvious reduction in sugarcane productivity as evident from a highly significant ($p=0.000$) and negative association ($T^c = -0.109$). Population growth stems into multiple socioeconomic problems of diverse nature. On one side, to meet the residential needs of unplanned population growth, the habitations and other associated physical infrastructure are spreading out and penetrating the natural areas and agricultural fields with great speed. On the side, fragmentation of land has made agriculture profession an uneconomic business to perform. Conversely, high economic opportunities for spending in housing and business require economic inputs. For all these reasons the farming communities are constrained to sell their agricultural lands to get instant finances for spending in other businesses or they themselves convert the agricultural land into residential colonies. Thus, sale of agricultural land for residential purpose is having a negative influence on agricultural production and subsequently on reduction of net income from the sale of agricultural products. Rahman et al. (2012) noticed that the density in village centers is increasing due to population growth. Moreover, due to overpopulation in these congested parts of villages, the land prices of the nearby surrounding village are increasing unprecedentedly. The high demand for such agricultural land for constructional purposes alongside high prices paid for it has initiated in chain reaction of selling agricultural lands for housing purposes. The economic outcomes of agricultural profession, according to Firman (1997),

cannot compete the high earning housing sector, thus, the farmers are more interested in selling their lands for residential and infrastructural purposes. Han and He (1999) made a comparison of spatial images of expanding villages and cities and established that due to development of real estate business the agriculture farms and fields are squeezing with high rate with each passing year. The authors further added that the investors have purchased huge agricultural lands for development of industrial estates and residential colonies in future due to which vast arable areas are left uncultivated for years. Asamoah (2010) further added that the agricultural lands stuck between residential colonies and industrial estates are choked for their water supply. Moreover, agricultural operations in such farms are quite expensive due to costly labor supply and high input and transportation costs. Consequently, the agricultural production and financial returns from sale of agricultural products are on decline in such farms (Asamoah, 2010; Rahman et al., 2012).

Furthermore, for all those respondents who perceived that investment in agriculture was not possible due to growing population needs for investments in other sectors like health, education etc. 20.6% earned above average net income from sale of sugarcane production compared to 56.6% of those who thought that investment in agriculture was equally important as investment in other sectors and 37.5% of those who were not certain in this respect. Low investment in agricultural sector than other sectors like health, education etc. constrained sugarcane productivity of the farmers to a greater extent as obvious from a highly significant ($p=0.000$) and negative ($T^c = -0.144$) association. Agriculture is a combination of science and art which requires technological inputs and skills for improved productivity. The farmers need not only to be acquainted with the knowledge and skills for agricultural production but also have to invest in innovative technologies and practices that ensure enhanced short and long-term production. Such investment in agricultural development is made by government and farmers conjointly. Thus, the government is leading these investments in ensuring supply of quality inputs on cheap rates, provision of agricultural machinery on subsidized rates and development of infrastructure for irrigation, transportation, storage, value addition and sale purposes etc. Moreover, the government also provides subsidies for purchase of excessive agricultural production. On the other hand, farmers are in leading role for micro level farming activities at the fields that include quality inputs, appropriate practices, proper care of land and crops, harvesting and sale of agricultural produce in such a way that land resources are not degraded, the crop losses are reduced, quality of the products are enhanced to earn high income. All these practices, whether on government or farmer's part, need financial inputs. However, due to growing population the agriculture sector has been shifted very low down in priority list by the government and to some extent by farmers as well. The government is investing high spending in other social sectors like health, education, industries etc. and a very meagre amount is allocated to agriculture sector. In the same line, the poor farmers have to prioritize the spending of their meager earning with high priority than health and education of family members than agriculture. Thus, low spending on agriculture becomes obvious and result into low sugarcane production in terms of meagre financial returns. These results are in line with the findings of Pervaiz et al. (2013) who stated that quality sugarcane production with high earning requires a specific micro-climate and substantial inputs in terms of quality seeds, fertilizers and irrigation etc. The high productive farmers are discouraged when they are paid very low prices for their sugarcane produced during crushing season. For some farmers these sale prices, if not subsidized by government, are so low that sugarcane production is a business of loss. Furthermore, the inputs required for sugarcane production are quite costly and the loans provided to the farmers are at a high interest rate. As a result, despite of high natural potential of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province to produce quality sugarcane crops, the sugarcane cropping areas are decreasing every year (Mandla et al., 2011). A government relief in this regard has proven fruitful in past to improve agricultural production of sugarcane (Dubb, 2013). According to Malaza and Myeni (2009) the fluctuated and inconsistent agricultural policies are creating distrust among farmers that result into uncertainty and fluctuation of the whole agricultural system. Goyal & Nash (2017) further probed the issue of financial investment by government in agriculture sector and reported that the meagre amount kept for agricultural development are inappropriately spend by the implementing agencies. As a result, the hot and burning issues of the farmers are not addressed properly by the government investment into agricultural sector (World Bank, 2018). Thus, the amount for spending in agriculture by the government needs not only to be enhanced but also to be spend in consultation with the farming communities through their active participation. This will result into a highly satisfied farmers with enhanced agricultural production to meet the national needs and raised income for the farmers (Goyal & Nash, 2017).

Conversely, the association of sugarcane productivity was non-significant with tremendous expansion in village habitation ($p=0.821$; $T^c = -0.012$). similar non-significant association was found between sugarcane productivity and use of arable land for commercial purpose like shops, markets etc. ($p=0.321$; $T^c = -0.047$). In line to above, the association of not allowing land to fallow naturally in lust of agricultural needs was found non-significant with sugarcane production ($p=0.424$; $T^c = -0.070$). Furthermore, sugarcane production and overcropping leading to sapping of soil nutrients exhibited a non-significant association ($p=0.386$; $T^c = -0.069$). In the same manner, scarcity of labor in rural areas due to lower wages exhibited a non-significant association with sugarcane productivity ($p=0.918$; $T^c = -0.005$). Among several variables and technical parameters of sugarcane productivity, the agricultural land area, site quality, and quality inputs are most important. Market

prices is another pull factor for enhancing sugarcane productivity and the resultant earning from it. The population growth factor is competing hard with the agricultural sector to grab more agricultural land and bring it under habitation. Moreover, excessive use of agricultural land exhaust the soil of its nutrients, reduce soil quality and lower down the agricultural production. Furthermore, intensification of agriculture is limited when the labor wages increase. Thus, the population growth leads to reduction of arable land, decline of soil quality and shortage of cheap labor supply that result into reduced agricultural production. However, these factors were not significant contributors in reducing sugarcane productivity in the study area. the probable reason was that despite of population growth, the agriculture land has not surpassed that threshold limit of reduced sugarcane production area. Moreover, the suitable agricultural land left for sugarcane production is properly cared of by farming communities through application of innovative technologies like fertilizers and nutritional supplements to the land due to which soil fertility is maintained to appropriate level. In addition, the population growth and unemployment constraint the youth population residing in the villages to be employed as agricultural labor willingly or unwillingly. Deng et al. (2015) also reported just a marginal effect of urbanization on agricultural land when population growth and urbanization is planned in appropriate manner. Malik and Ali (2015) further added the problem of low productivity from squeezing agricultural land can be overcome by adopting innovative technologies. Therefore, for some optimists, on the face of technological development, the loss of agricultural production is not a threat (WB and DRC, 2014; Song and Pijanowski, 2014; Francis et al., 2013). The findings of Malik and Ali (2015), however, negate these results by declaring that population growth is playing havoc in reducing agricultural production through reducing land area and exhausting its soil from minerals, nutrients and vitality. Wang et al. (2013) further added that on the face of rapid urban and population growth, the farming communities have swiftly adopted, maintained and enhanced agricultural productivity by implying functional agricultural practices and innovative technologies (Tan et al., 2009). The developed and developing nations are implementing new policies to control land, air and water pollution and consume solid waste for some constructive purposes, not only to ensure to reuse of resources but also to maintain soil health (Chen, 2007; Yang et al., 2003). Furthermore, timely availability of labor for agricultural operations is important for enhancing agricultural production (Khan and Khan, 2015). However, the agriculture sector is facing the problem of labor shortage due to low wages paid to them (Sabyasachi and Chetana, 2017). However, in growing population and low employment opportunities, the industrial labors are becoming surplus and constrained to get employment in low paid agriculture sector (Li et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2013). Moreover, engagement of women as a cheaply available labor source is replacing highly paid male labor (Wang et al., 2013). The developed nations have overcome the problems of labor supply by devising innovative technologies and machineries to avoid the involvement of excessive labor (Prabakar et al. 2011). Thus, technologies are looking for innovative solutions for anthropogenic problems to maintain and enhance agricultural production (Li, 2015).

In nutshell, high population growth is exerting pressure on agriculture sector by bringing more and more agricultural land under residential area. The growth of habitation has both demographic and economic causes behind it as due to population growth and fragmented agricultural land, the agriculture profession is not as much income earning as is the business of housing and other associated businesses. Thus, it is not only the land converted to the residential area, but the farmers too are converted to real estate businessmen. On the other side, the declining agricultural sector is in dire need of government intervention for its financial and technical support to sustain and uplift agricultural production. However, the government has kept agriculture on low priority, and subordinate to housing, health, education sectors due to which any amount left from these sectors is spent on agricultural development. The meagre amount allocated for the development of agriculture sector, too, is spent in isolation without the active involvement of farmers. As a result, the expected results of government expenses in agriculture sector are rarely achieved. An improved agricultural policy to stop conversion of agricultural land into other land uses and active involvement of farming communities in development projects that are meant for enhancing agricultural production can ensure enhanced sugarcane production through its improved net income.

Table 3 Association between population growth and sugarcane productivity of the respondents

Attributes	Attitude	Sugarcane productivity (in terms of net income)				Statistics χ^2 (P-Value) T^c
		Above average net income	Average net income	Below average net income	Total	
Your village habitat is expanded tremendously	Yes	91 (27.6)	126 (38.2)	113 (34.2)	330 (100)	$\chi^2 = 1.533$ (0.821) $T^c = -0.012$
	No	11 (30.6)	12 (33.3)	13 (36.1)	36 (100)	
	Uncertain	7 (38.9)	5 (27.8)	6 (33.3)	18 (100)	
People are selling their	Yes	44 (19.6)	102 (45.3)	79 (35.1)	225 (100)	$\chi^2 = 25.573$

lands for residential purposes	No	57 (41.9)	33 (24.3)	46 (33.8)	136 (100)	(0.000) T ^c =-0.109
	Uncertain	8 (34.8)	8 (34.8)	7 (30.4)	23 (100)	
People at your village use arable land for commercial purposes (shops, markets)	Yes	73 (27.7)	97 (36.5)	96 (36.1)	266 (100)	x ² =4.689 (0.321) T ^c =-0.047
	No	25 (26.6)	39 (41.5)	30 (31.9)	94 (100)	
The land is not allowed to fallow naturally in lust of agricultural needs of growing population	Yes	47 (31.1)	61 (40.4)	43 (28.5)	151 (100)	x ² =3.870 (0.424) T ^c =0.070
	No	57 (26.6)	75 (35)	82 (38.3)	214(100)	
	Uncertain	5 (26.3)	7 (36.8)	7 (36.8)	19 (100)	
It is due to overpopulation that investment in agriculture is not possible because population needs investment in other sectors like health, education etc.	Yes	55 (20.6)	113 (42.3)	99 (37.1)	267 (100)	x ² =32.202 (0.000) T ^c =-0.144
	No	39 (50.6)	14 (18.2)	24 (31.2)	77 (100)	
	Uncertain	15 (37.5)	16 (40)	9 (22.5)	40 (100)	
It is due to overpopulation that over cropping occurs which leads to sapping of soil nutrients	Yes	63 (25.9)	90 (37)	90 (37)	243 (100)	x ² =4.152 (0.386) T ^c =-0.069
	No	34 (30.9)	44 (40)	32 (29.1)	110 (100)	
	Uncertain	12 (38.7)	9 (29)	10 (32.3)	31 (100)	
Mostly there is scarcity of labors rural area because of low wages	Yes	78 (28.9)	97 (35.9)	95 (35.2)	270 (100)	x ² =0.943 (0.918) T ^c =-0.005
	No	21 (28)	29 (38.7)	25 (33.3)	75 (100)	
	Uncertain	10 (25.6)	17 (43.6)	12 (30.8)	39 (100)	

Percentages are given in parenthesis

Association between population growth and sugarcane productivity (controlling socioeconomic status of the respondents)

Results in table 4 show that for those respondents from high socio-economic status who perceived high influence of population growth, 37.2% earned above average net income from sugarcane sale compared to 44.4% of those who perceived moderate influence of population growth and 53.8% with low perceiving of influence population growth. In addition, for all those respondents from middle socio-economic status who perceived high influence of population growth, 18.4% earned above average net income from sugarcane sale as compared 25.4% of those who perceived moderate influence of population growth and 31% of those who perceived low influence of population growth. Furthermore, for all those respondents from low socio-economic status who had high population influence, 16.1% earned above average net income from sugarcane sale compared 33.3% of those who perceived moderate and 30.4% with perceiving low influence of population growth. The association between population growth and net income from sugarcane production was found non-significant ($p=0.493$) and negative ($T^c = -0.068$) for high socio-economic group. The association of these variables was highly significant and negative ($P=0.000$; $T^c = -0.228$) for middle socio-economic group. Likewise, the association of the above said variables was significant and negative ($P=0.050$ & $T^c = -0.275$) for low-income groups. Value of level of significance and T^c for entire table show highly significant and negative ($P=0.000$ & $T^c = -0.188$) association between population growth and sugarcane productivity for all the three socio-economic groups. Variation in Kendal T^c and chi square significance values for all the three socio-economic groups indicated that association of population growth and sugarcane productivity is spurious on the basis of socio-economic statuses of the respondents, where middle and low socio-economic group farmers face reduction in sugarcane production at a higher rate than the high socioeconomic status farmers, due to population growth.

Poverty and population growth are conjoined to each other. Therefore, the rate of population growth and its associated spread of habitation through encroachment into agricultural land is a common observable entity in villages dominated by low and middle socioeconomic farmers. On the other side, the high socioeconomic status farmers are more literate and acquainted with the technologies related to population control on one side and enhancing agricultural production on the other side. Consequently, the population growth is an additional burden on middle and low socioeconomic status farmers to reduce their agricultural production due to reduced land size. In addition, the crops produced by such farmers are mostly consumed at family level with a very meager amount spared for sale. Thus, the agriculture of middle and low socioeconomic status farmers is mostly for subsistence and least for the commercial income from sale of agricultural products. Karim (2013) pointed out that high population growth is at the root cause of declining agricultural production.

The negative influences of population growth on agricultural production are diverse, multifaceted and complex (Karim, 2011), ranging from land fragmentation, land disputes and urbanization to exhaustive use of land resources to meet the needs of growing population (Buchholz, 1993). Rehman et al. (2012) illustrated that the agricultural land is converted into habitation to meet the needs of growing population. Moreover, the demanding prices of agricultural land for construction industry accelerated the conversion process of agriculture into habitation (Firman, 1997). As a result, the agricultural land, especially in low socioeconomic suburbs, is squeezing dramatically (Han and He, 1999). The left-over agricultural lands are mostly surrounded by habitations and face the problems of land pollution, water pollution and low water supply (Asamoah, 2010; Rehman et al., 2012). The low and middle socioeconomic status farmers find it difficult to maintain the productive capacity of their lands through improved inputs (Pervaiz et al., 2013). The World Bank (2018), therefore, rightly emphasized on the governments to control their population growth and revise their agricultural policies on priority basis to overcome the potential problems of high food insecurity in future at national and international levels (Goyal & Nash, 2017).

Table 4 Association between influence of population growth and sugarcane productivity (controlling socio-economic status of the respondents)

Socio-economic status	Relationship with population growth	Net Income				Statistics χ^2 (P-Value) T^c =	Level of significance for the entire table
		Above average net income	Average net income	Below average net income	Total		
High socioeconomic status	High influence	16 (37.2)	17 (39.5)	10 (23.3)	43 (100)	χ^2 =3.402 (0.493) T^c =-0.068	χ^2 =24.068 (0.000) T^c =-0.188
	Moderate influence	8 (44.4)	5 (27.8)	5 (27.8)	18 (100)		
	Low influence	14 (53.8)	5 (19.2)	7 (26.9)	26 (100)		
	Total	38 (43.7)	27 (31)	22 (25.3)	87 ((100)		
Middle socioeconomic status	High influence	19 (18.4)	30 (29.1)	54 (52.4)	103 (100)	χ^2 =24.381 (0.000) T^c =-0.228	
	Moderate influence	17 (25.4)	36 (53.7)	14 (20.9)	67 (100)		
	Low influence	18 (31)	27 (46.6)	13 (22.4)	58 (100)		
	Total	54 (23.7)	93 (40.8)	81 (35.5)	228 (100)		
Low socioeconomic status	High influence	5 (16.1)	7 (22.6)	19 (61.3)	31 (100)	χ^2 =9.469 (0.050) T^c =-0.275	
	Moderate influence	5 (33.3)	5 (33.3)	5 (33.3)	15 (100)		
	Low influence	7 (30.4)	11 (47.8)	5 (21.7)	23 (100)		
	Total	17 (24.6)	23 (33.3)	29 (42)	69 (100)		

Percentages are given in parenthesis

Conclusions and recommendations

It is concluded from the study that population if unchecked will cause multiple problems for agricultural development. Due to population growth, fertile lands are used for housing purposes, for commercial or industrial purposes which not only limit the fertile agricultural land but also the waste materials from these places make hazardous the soil and limiting its productivity. Moreover, due to land fragmentation in the families due to increased number of heirs, the small fragments are not cultivable and farmers either left it uncultivable or sell it and start business or migrated into cities for white-collar jobs which negatively affect productivity of sugarcane and other crops. The study recommended that through the diffusion and adoption of new technologies by the farmers, the involvement of influential community leaders both religious and political for awareness in controlling population and devising and implementing such strategies that balance the population growth on one side and enhance per unit area agricultural production on the other side can be beneficial for enhancing sugarcane production.

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